

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXXIV. BROMINATION AND NITRATION OF 4-KETO-1:4-DIHYDRO-2:3-POLYMETHYLENEQUINOLINES

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Monobromination, dibromination, nitration and dinitration of 2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone (I), 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline (II) and 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline (III) have been studied. Compounds (II) and (III) have been synthesised by condensing anthranilic acid with cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone respectively.

In continuation of our study on the bromination and nitration of 1-methyl- and 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridones (Desai *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 86), we have extended this investigation to the case of 2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone, prepared from anthranilic acid and 3-methylcyclohexanone by Tiedke's method (Ber., 1909, 42, 621). As it was thought interesting to study the effect of a pentamethylene and a hexamethylene ring for comparison with that of the tetramethylene ring, which is present in the tetrahydroacridones, we have synthesised the requisite compounds by condensing anthranilic acid with cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone respectively by the same method (*loc. cit.*). In each case the intermediate anils were isolated at low temperatures, and their cyclisation at high temperature afforded the desired products. These compounds have been named as the derivatives of dihydroquinoline. Thus, compound (II) is named as 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline, and compound (III) as 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline. Tetrahydroacridone itself can be named for comparison as 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-tetramethylenequinoline (I).

(I : $n=4$)

(II : $n=5$)

(III : $n=6$)

Bromination of 2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone afforded a mixture of 7-bromo and 9-bromo derivatives, and a 7:9-dibromo derivative on dibromination. Similarly bromination of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline furnished mainly the 8-bromo derivative accompanied by a small amount of 6-bromo isomer. 4-Keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline on bromination gave also a mixture of equal amounts of 6-bromo and 8-bromo derivatives, while 6:8-dibromo derivatives were obtained in each case on dibromination.

2-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone on nitration afforded an equimolecular mixture of 7-nitro and 9-nitro derivatives, while 7:9-dinitro derivative was obtained on dinitration. Similarly 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline and 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline on nitration gave a mixture of 6-nitro and 8-nitro derivatives wherein the 8-nitro isomer predominated, while dinitration gave 6:8-dinitro derivative in each case. The authentic specimens for comparison were prepared by condensing appropriately substituted anthranilic acids with 3-methylcyclohexanone, cycloheptanone, and cyclooctanone respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-o-Carboxyanilino-5-methyl- Δ^{12} -cycloheptene.— A mixture of anthranilic acid (5 g.) and cycloheptanone (5 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 120° for 3 hours. The product was washed with a little benzene to remove the impurities, and the residue was crystallised from benzene in colorless prisms, m.p. 140°, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 72.5; H, 7.1. $C_{14}O_2N$ requires C, 72.7; H, 7.4%).

4-Keto-1:4 dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—The above anil was heated in an oil bath at 220° for 2 hours. The solid after treating with a dilute NaHCO_3 solution to remove the unchanged material was crystallised from benzene in small colorless plates, m.p. 335°. (Found: C, 78.0; H, 6.5; N, 6.32. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}$ requires C, 78.9; H, 7.0; N, 6.57%).

6- & 8-Bromo-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinolines.—A solution of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline (4.26 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) with a trace of iodine was cooled to 5°. A 20% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.) was next added gradually with stirring. After stirring the mixture for one hour at 10°, it was kept in an ice box for 24 hours and poured into water. The solid separating was filtered off, washed, dried, and finally crystallised from 90% ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 329°, yield 2.56 g. This was proved to be the 8-bromo derivative by its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen synthesised from 3-bromoanthranilic acid and cycloheptanone. (Found: Br, 27.27. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONBr}$ requires Br, 27.49%).

The mother liquor on concentration gave a solid, which after several crystallisations from ethanol furnished brownish white needles, m.p. 340°, yield 0.12 g. This was shown to be 6-bromo derivative by its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen obtained from 5-bromoanthranilic acid and cycloheptanone. (Found: Br, 27.29. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONBr}$ requires Br, 27.49%).

Synthesis of 6-Bromo-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—5-Bromoanthranilic acid (2.16 g.) and cycloheptanone (1.12 g.) were heated in an oil bath at 240° for 3 hours. The product after usual purification was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol in brownish needles, m.p. 340°, undepressed by admixture with the product obtained by the direct bromination of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline. (Found: Br, 27.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONBr}$: Br, 27.49%).

Synthesis of 8-Bromo-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—3-Bromoanthranilic acid (2.16 g.) and cycloheptanone (1.12 g.) were heated in an oil bath at 210-20° for 2 hours, the temperature being gradually raised. The solid after the usual purification was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 329°, undepressed by admixture with the product obtained by direct bromination of 4-keto-1:4 dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline. (Found: Br, 27.68. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONBr}$: Br, 27.49%).

6:8-Dibromo-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—To a solution of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline (2.13 g.) in glacial acetic acid (12 c.c.) with a trace of iodine, cooled to 5°, was added slowly a 20% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (16 c.c.). After keeping the mixture in an ice bath for 24 hours, it was poured into water and the solid was filtered, washed, dried, and crystallised from absolute ethanol in light brown needles, m.p. 325°, yield 3.0 g. It was identified as 6-8-dibromo derivative by mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen obtained from 3:5-dibromoanthranilic acid and cycloheptanone. The same product can also be obtained by the bromination of either 6-bromo or 8-bromo derivative. (Found: Br, 43.00. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ONBr}_2$: Br, 43.24%).

Synthesis of 6:8-Dibromo-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—A mixture of 3:5-dibromoanthranilic acid (2.63 g.) and cycloheptanone (1.12 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180° for 1 hour and then at 230° for further one hour. The pasty mass was triturated with petrol b.p. 40-50° and then with ether. The residue was crystallised from 90% ethanol in light brown needles, m.p. 325°, undepressed by admixture with the dibromo derivative obtained by the direct bromination of the original product. (Found: Br, 43.45. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{O}_{12}\text{ONBr}_2$: Br, 43.24%).

6-&8-Nitro-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinolines.—A solution of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline (2.13 g.) in H_2SO_4 (d 1.89, 15 c.c.) was cooled to -5°. A mixture

of HNO_3 (d 1.49, 0.42 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 c.c.), cooled to -5° , was added to the above cooled solution with constant stirring. After keeping the mixture in an ice bath for 12 hours it was poured in ice water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow plates, m.p. 355° , yield 0.85 g. This was proved to be 8-nitro derivative on comparison with the authentic specimen prepared from 3-nitroanthranilic acid and cycloheptanone. (Found: N, 10.70. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.86%).

The yellowish mother liquor on concentration and cooling deposited a solid, which after several crystallisations from ethanol afforded orange-yellow microcrystals, m.p. 277° . This was shown to be the 6-nitro derivative on comparison with the authentic specimen. (Found: N, 10.62. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.86%).

Synthesis of 6-Nitro-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—A mixture of 5-nitroanthranilic acid (3.64 g.) and cycloheptanone (2.24 g.) was heated at $120-30^\circ$ for 2 hours and then at 230° for further 3 hours. The product was washed with benzene to remove the impurities and then crystallised from 90% ethanol in orange-yellow microcrystals, m.p. 277° . The m.p. showed no depression when mixed with the second isomer obtained by the direct nitration of the 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline. (Found: N, 11.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: N, 10.86%).

Synthesis of 8-Nitro-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—A mixture of 3-nitroanthranilic acid (3.64 g.) and cycloheptanone (2.24 g.) was heated at $120-30^\circ$ for 2 hours and then at 230° for further 2 hours. The product was crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow plates, m.p. 355° , undepressed by admixture with the product obtained by direct nitration of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline. (Found: N, 10.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$: N, 10.86%).

6:8-Dinitro-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—A nitrating mixture of HNO_3 (d 1.49, 0.84 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 c.c.), cooled to -5° , was slowly added to the cooled solution of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline (2.13 g.) in H_2SO_4 (d 1.89, 15 c.c.). After keeping the mixture in an ice bath for 14 hours, it was poured on crushed ice. The precipitated solid was finally crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow plates, yield 2.0 g., m.p. 357° , undepressed on admixture with the authentic specimen. The same product was also obtained by direct nitration of either 6-nitro or 8-nitro derivative. (Found: N, 13.62. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.90%).

Synthesis of 6:8-Dinitro-4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline.—A mixture of 3:5-dinitroanthranilic acid (4.5 g.) and cycloheptanone (2.24 g.) was heated in an oil bath at $130-40^\circ$ for 2 hours and further at $220-30^\circ$ for 2 hours. The product on crystallisation from ethanol furnished pale yellow plates, m.p. 357° , undepressed by admixture with the dinitro compound obtained by nitration of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-pentamethylenequinoline. (Found: N, 13.58. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{N}_4$: N, 13.9%).

1-o-Carboxyanilino- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclooctene.—A mixture of anthranilic acid (5 g.) and cyclooctanone (8 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 120° for 3 hours. The solid after washing with little benzene to remove the impurities was crystallised from benzene in colorless, small prisms, m.p. 125° , yield 5.7 g. (Found: C, 73.21; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 73.40; H, 7.7%).

4-Keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline.—The above anil was heated in an oil bath at 220° for 2 hours. The solid after being treated with a dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate was crystallised from benzene in colorless, small plates, m.p. 323° . (Found: C, 78.6; H, 7.3; N, 5.87. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}$ requires C, 79.2; H, 7.4; N, 6.16%).

TABLE I

[Q = 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinoline]

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	*Cryst shape.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	6-Bromo-Q	340°	Colorless needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ONBr	Br: 25.96%	26.14%
2.	8-Bromo-Q	305°	Light brown needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ONBr	Br: 26.00	26.14
3.	6:8-Dibromo-Q	305°	Brown needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ONBr ₂	Br: 41.24	41.55
4.	6-Nitro-Q	348°	Pale yellow microcrystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.06	10.29
5.	8-Nitro-Q	352°	Dark orange microcrystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.09	10.29
6.	6:8-Dinitro-Q	356°	Do	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄	N: 13.40	13.22

* All crystallised from ethanol, the last compound (6) from absolute ethanol.

N.B. The authentic specimens of compounds 1, 2 and 3 were synthesised by condensing 5-bromo-, 3-bromo- and 3:5-dibromo-anthranilic acids with cyclooctanone and the compounds 4, 5 and 6 were synthesised by condensing 5-nitro-, 3-nitro- and 3:5-dinitro-anthranilic acids with cyclooctanone by the method described above for comparison.

TABLE II

[A = 2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone]

No.	Compound.	M.P.	*Cryst. form.	Mol. formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	7-Bromo-A	327°	Yellowish needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONBr	Br: 27.15%	27.39%
2.	9-Bromo-A	342°	**Colorless needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONBr	Br: 27.19	27.39
3.	7:9-Dibromo-A	315°	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONBr ₂	Br: 42.93	43.12
4.	7-Nitro-A	310°	**Canary yellow plates	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.60	10.85
5.	9-Nitro-A	350°	Pale yellow needles	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.66	10.85
6.	7:9-Dinitro-A	340°	**Yellowish orange micro-crystals	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	N: 14.10	14.53

* From ethanol.

** From absolute ethanol.

N.B. The authentic specimens of compounds 1, 2 and 3 were synthesised by condensing 5-bromo-, 3-bromo- and 3:5-dibromo-anthranilic acids with 3-methylcyclohexanone and compounds 4, 5 and 6 by condensing 5-nitro-, 3-nitro- and 3:5-dinitro-anthranilic acids with 3-methylcyclohexanone by the method described above.

The bromo and nitro derivatives obtained by the monobromination, dibromination, mononitration, and dinitration of 4-keto-1:4-dihydro-2:3-hexamethylenequinolines are shown in Table I. Those of 2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone are listed in Table II. Their constitution: were proved by mixed m.p. with the authentic specimens.